

Fostering Technology for Sustainable Societal Development: An Empirical Evaluation of the Impact

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Abstract: The global pursuit of sustainability highlights the crucial role of technology as a key enabler for achieving United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). However, this relationship is complex and not inherently positive. This study provides an empirical evaluation of the impact of technology on sustainable societal development across six countries (Finland, USA, China, India, South Africa and Nigeria) from 2020 to 2024. Using Socio-Technical Systems (STS) and Technological Innovation Systems (TIS) frameworks, we employ panel regression analysis to test hypotheses on the direct impact of technology and the mediating roles of policy, skills and infrastructure on triple bottom line (TBL). Our findings shows that the impact of technology is targeted and sector-specific rather than automatic. While agricultural mechanization enhances economic growth and food security, and e-health technology improve life expectancy, general technology adoption does not necessarily reduce poverty or enhance education. Furthermore, technology can increase CO₂ emissions, highlighting environmental trade-offs. The study concludes that technology is a significant yet incomplete driver of sustainability, and its benefits are maximized only when supported by targeted investments in key enablers such as infrastructure and skills.

Keywords: Sustainable Societal Development, Socio-Technical Systems (STS), Technological Innovation Systems (TIS), Triple Bottom Line (TBL).

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability has become one of the most defining challenges in present time, with pressures mounting from climate change, resource depletion, and growing social inequalities. This led to the creation of the United Nation's (UN's) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015, with the aim of achieving global sustainability across 17 interdependent global objectives by 2030 [1]. Within this context, technological innovation is increasingly seen as a catalyst for sustainable societal development [2]. Modern technologies ranging from artificial intelligence (AI), renewable energy, smart infrastructure and precision agriculture are now being deployed to tackle complex challenges and improve quality of life across diverse domains [3]. These innovations play a crucial role in addressing the three pillars of sustainability – economy, environment, and society [2]. This development aligns with the vision of the UNs SDGs, given that digital solutions can directly contribute to roughly

70% of the SDG targets and help accelerate progress particularly in areas such as financial inclusion,

effective governance, and poverty reduction [3]. Empirical evidence also shows that countries which expanded digital infrastructure and affordable connectivity in the past decade have achieved significantly faster and more inclusive gains in human development, productivity, and environmental outcomes compared to those who have not [4, 5].

However, the relationship between technology and sustainability is not inherently linear or always positive. This is because not all innovations automatically yield positive outcomes for society [6]. Many promising technologies face obstacles such as unequal access, high costs, and misalignment with local needs; and if poorly managed they can further increase inequalities or introduce new risks [7]. For example, digital divides and lack of access

can leave marginalized groups behind, and concerns such as data breaches or job displacement show that technology's impact can be double-edged. Meanwhile, global progress on sustainable development remains uneven, with nearly half of the 169 UN's SDG targets showing weak or insufficient progress, and about one-third having stalled or regressed [5]. These challenges highlight a critical need to evaluate when and how technology truly contributes to sustainable societal development, as opposed to when its potential falls short.

While several studies have examined the factors driving technology adoption, they often overlook how technology use affects long-term development outcomes. Beyond asking whether people accept or implement a new technology, there is a need to understand the actual impact of that technology on economic, environmental and social metrics of sustainability. To address this gap, this study presents an empirical evaluation of technology's impact on sustainable development across diverse domains, while taking into account socio-technical systems (STS) and technological innovation systems (TIS) frameworks. Using data from 6 selected countries, this study examines how the uptake of various technologies relates to improvements in key sectors ranging from agriculture, education, energy, and healthcare. It investigates the extent to which technological innovations in these areas translate into measurable gains such as food security, enhanced educational access, greater energy efficiency, or improved health outcomes. Additionally, the study explores which factors or conditions (policy, skill and infrastructure quality) mediate the magnitude of these impacts. By quantitatively investigating these questions, this study aims to shed light on the real-world contribution of technology toward advancing societal development goals. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 focuses on the subject literature and theoretical background; Section 3 describes the research methodology and data sources; Section 4 presents the results of the quantitative analysis and discusses the findings; and Section 5 concludes the study and offer recommendation for policy and practice

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Sustainable societal development requires that progress balance the three interdependent pillars of sustainability: environmental protection, economic prosperity, and social inclusion [8]. This triad which is known as the tiple-bottom-line (TBL) asserts that long-term societal progress should not only be measured by economic performance but also by social impact and environmental responsibility [9].

In practice this means that policy makers and various governmental and non-governmental institutions must consider the welfare of society alongside ecological integrity when accessing projects or policies impacted by technology. The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB) provide guidelines for quantifying Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) metrics across the TBL [9].

Since the adoption of the UN's SDGs in 2015, various researchers have highlighted how the TBL aligns with SDG targets, and also how organizations adopting the GRI-based TBL frameworks tend to be more transparent about social and environmental performance, thereby propelling societal sustainability [9, 10, 11, 12]. Recent survey of ESG research further shows that since 2015 there has been an exponential growth in publications relating to circular economy initiatives, alternative energy solutions and green business models [9].

However, this work builds on the TBL, by linking and evaluating how technology impacts sustainable societal development. To properly understand how technology impacts developmental outcomes, it is inadequate to examine technology in isolation; its impact is shaped by complex interaction between technology and societal structures [9]. Geel et al., [13] emphasized that technologies must be examined within the context of the socio-technical systems (STS) they inhabit. They also showed that sustainable societal development requires restructuring consumption-production systems, as innovation alone is insufficient because outcomes are dependent on interactions among technologies, markets, governance, culture, and infrastructure. For example, a precision agriculture system may be ineffective without supporting land tenure policies, farmer training programs, and accessible digital platforms.

Also, the technological innovation systems (TIS) framework provides a clearer understanding of how technology impacts sustainable societal development. It emphasizes that technological evaluation and adoption depend on an ecosystem that involves actors, institutions, and interactions that drive the development and use of a technology [14]. Applying the TIS framework allows a proper analysis of why a particular technology thrives in one economy but struggles in another. For example, the global effort to promote solar energy through renewable energy technology depends heavily on the technological innovation system. It will require institutions of learning and companies to generate and share knowledge to manufacture and install them, entrepreneurs and marketers to test business

models and market them, and supportive policies to create markets and confer legitimacy. If any of these functions are weak, it may be difficult for the system to deliver social and environmental benefits, even if the technology itself is innovative.

Table 1 summarizes key related works, highlighting the focus of each work and their specific limitation, which this work aims to address.

While this study builds on the TBL, by linking and evaluating how technology impacts sustainable societal development, the reviewed literature points to several gaps that this study aims to address. These gaps are addressed by conducting an empirical evaluation of how technology adoption across agriculture, education, energy and healthcare sectors relate to sustainable societal development using 6 selected countries as case studies. We apply STS and TIS perspectives in order to identify mediating factors (policy skills, and infrastructure) using the TBL framework to assess social, environmental and economic outcomes.

	Telemedicine Network; defines sustainability and emphasises governance, CO ₂ reduction and ethical factors.	quantitative assessment of socio-economic benefits.
Ramli <i>et al.</i> 2024 [18]	Systematic review of smart-city technologies and user behaviour; proposes a Sustainable Smart City Network.	Provides conceptual framework; lacks empirical evidence on energy savings or social impacts.
Ogunniye <i>et al.</i> 2024 [19]	Conceptualization of socio-technical systems; emphasises interdependence of social and technical subsystems.	Theoretical; does not apply STS framework to specific technologies or sectors.
Abhulimen <i>et al.</i> 2024 [20]	Developed an automated lighting control system using Arduino and ultrasonic sensors for households with physically disabled persons. Aimed to improve energy efficiency and accessibility while keeping costs low.	Narrow scope, focused solely on lighting; does not consider other sectors and socio-technical dynamics; lacks analysis of policy, market and institutional factors that may influence adoption and scalability.
Hasnat <i>et al.</i> 2025 [21]	Review of water microgrids; proposes triple-top-line approach to maximise social, economic and environmental value.	Review; limited to water infrastructure; lacks empirical analysis.

TABLE 1: SUMMARY OF REVIEWED LITERATURE

Authors (Year)	Focus of Study	Limitation relative to this work
Mishra and Pandey, 2025 [9]	Bibliometric analysis of triple-bottom-line research; focuses on growth and shift towards circular economy and green business models.	Descriptive; lacks analysis of the impact of technology on sustainability outcomes.
Liao, 2023 [10]	Triple-bottom-line assessment of green energy projects; shows renewable energy projects can deliver economic growth, reduction of emissions and access to electricity.	Sector-specific; does not explore socio-technical factors or cross-sector impacts.
Stanimirović <i>et al.</i> 2025 [12]	Analysis of renewable-energy investments in European countries using the TBL; finds positive energy and economic outcomes but uncertain employment effects.	Focused on energy sector; does not investigate technology adoption in other domains; no socio-technical analysis.
Bergek <i>et al.</i> , 2019 [14]	Review of the technological innovation systems framework; identifies critical functions like knowledge development, market formation and legitimization.	Conceptual; no empirical application to sustainable development metrics.
Addoriso <i>et al.</i> 2025 [15]	Scoping review on adoption of innovative technologies in agriculture; highlights inconsistent treatment of adoption factors and importance of extension services.	Examines adoption but not long-term sustainability impacts; single sector (agriculture); ignores socio-technical interactions.
Ozen <i>et al.</i> 2024 [16]	Hypothetical study estimating travel, carbon and wage savings if telemedicine replaced follow-up visits in a Turkish clinic.	Uses hypothetical scenario; limited to one clinic; does not measure health outcomes or address access and equity issues.
Rizos <i>et al.</i> 2025 [17]	Analysis of sustainability in the Greek National	Conceptual and context-specific; lacks

3. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology adopted for this study. The study employs a quantitative research design using secondary panel data to evaluate the impact of technology on sustainable societal development across 6 selected countries (Finland, United States of America (USA.), China, India, South Africa, Nigeria) and 4 sectors (agriculture, education, energy and healthcare).

3.1 Research Methodology Design

In this study, a hypothetico-deductive approach was employed. It involves:

- i. Developing hypotheses based on the STS and TIS (TIS) frameworks.
- ii. Collecting and analyzing quantitative data to test the hypotheses.
- iii. Drawing inferences about the mediating factors that impact the technology-sustainability relationship (Empirical analysis strategy).

The design is a cross-sectional time-series analysis which allows the observation of variables across multiple countries and sectors over a period of 5 years (2020-2024) to capture the post-SDG era and the most recent period for which comprehensive data is available.

3.2 Development of Hypotheses

Based on the STS and TIS frameworks, the general hypothesis structure of this work test whether technology adoption improves societal sustainability along the TBL dimensions (economic, environmental and social), and whether that effect is dependent on mediating factors of policy, skills and infrastructure. The hypothesis structure is given as follows:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Test the direct relationship between technology and sustainable societal development.

Hypotheses 2-4 (H2-H4): Test the contingent relationship based on the STS and TIS context.

3.2.1 General Hypothesis

H1: Technology adoption (number of internet users used as a proxy) has a significant positive impact of sustainable societal development, leading to:

- **H1a (Economic):** increased economic outcomes such as GDP per capita growth and reduced poverty headcount ratio.
- **H1b (Social):** increase in life expectancy at birth and school enrollment.
- **H1c (Environmental):** improved environmental outcomes such as lower CO₂ emissions per unit of output and increase in renewable energy consumption.

H2 (Policy mediation): The positive relationship in H1a-c are significantly stronger in countries with higher levels of regulatory quality.

H3 (Skills mediation): The positive relationship in H1a-c are stronger in countries with higher levels of mean years of education or training.

H4 (Infrastructure mediation): The positive relationship in H1a-c are significantly stronger in countries with better and quality infrastructure such as electricity, good network coverage, trade and transport.

3.2.2 Sector-Specific Hypothesis

• Agriculture

H5: Adoption of agricultural machinery is associated with:

- Economic: Increase in GDP per capita.
- Social: Reduced hunger or increase in food production index.
- Environmental: lower CO₂ emission intensity.

H6: The relationship in H5 is significantly stronger in countries with good policies, access to adequate and proper farmer training programs (skills), and quality trade and transport infrastructure.

• Education

H7: Integration of digital technologies in education (schools with internet access) is associated with:

- Economic: Increased government expenditure on education.
- Social: Higher primary education enrollment rate.
- Environmental: Reduction in CO₂ emission from transportation as a result of remote learning.

H8: The relationship in H7 is stronger in countries with good regulatory policies; teachers with high mean years of training (skills); and countries with good network infrastructure.

• Energy

H9: Increased adoption of renewable energy and distributed clean energy solutions as seen in improved access to electricity, is associated with:

- Economic: Macroeconomic growth and stability seen in GDP per capita growth.
- Social: Equitable and decentralized energy distribution, as seen in increase in rural access to electricity.
- Environmental: Reduction in CO₂ emissions and increase in renewable energy share in total final energy consumption (TFEC %).

H10: The relationship in H9 is significantly stronger in countries with supportive policies, robust national grid as seen in electric power consumption per capita (infrastructure) and increase in mean years of training for workers in the energy sector (skills).

• Healthcare

H11: Integration of technology-enabled healthcare is associated with:

- Economic: Improved current health expenditure.
- Social: Improved life expectancy at birth.
- Environmental: Reduction in CO₂ emissions as a result of physical travels for treatment.

H12: The relationship in H11 is stronger in countries with clear data privacy regulations for digital health (policy); high density of trained physicians (skills); and good network infrastructure.

3.3 Data Collection and Analysis Strategy

The study develops a panel dataset for six selected countries (Finland, USA, China, India, South Africa, Nigeria) over a period of 5 years (2020-2024). The dataset considers the same factors for each of the 6